

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-174-AD-H-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 174
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/7/2022 10:29:08 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 8:36:35 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.479	156499	20.31	6241
2	15.828	228876	29.70	8227
3	16.868	162439	21.08	5313
4	21.053	222785	28.91	6109

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-215-ADH-2% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20220112
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 215
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/12/2023 19:09:02 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 20:32:41 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	15.043	2809	0.10	175
2	16.438	10162	0.36	574
3	17.292	2692293	96.34	97257
4	21.688	89295	3.20	2862